

Sulphodichlorohydroxydimethyl Fuchson Dicarboxylic Acid as a Colorimetric Reagent for the Microdetermination of Beryllium

Surendra Nath Sinha and Arun K. Dey

Beryllium forms a pink-coloured chelate ($\lambda_{\max}$ 540 m μ) with Chrome Azurol S (sulphodichlorohydroxydimethyl fuchson dicarboxylic acid, colour index 723). This has been used in the colorimetric determination of beryllium on a micro scale and conditions for the measurements have been worked out. Beer's law is adhered to with 0.01 to 0.33 p.p.m. of beryllium in presence of a large excess of Chrome Azurol S. Measurements may be made over a wide range of temperature between pH 4.0 and 6.8. The sensitivity is 0.00045 γ /cm² (Sandell) and 0.0045 γ /cm² (practical). Copper, aluminium, iron, thorium, zirconium, borate, carbonate, oxalate, and citrate interfere in the determination.

In a recent communication Dey *et al.*¹ reported that sulphodichlorohydroxydimethyl fuchson dicarboxylic acid (Chrome Azurol S, colour index 723) formed stable coloured chelates in aqueous solution with a large number of cations including Cu(II), Be(II), Mg(II), Cd(II), Al(III), Co(IV), La(III), Pb(IV), Ti(IV), Zr(IV), U(VI), Fe(III), Co(II), and Ni(II) under specific experimental conditions. They also reported that beryllium² formed a pink-coloured chelate ($\lambda_{\max}$ 540 m μ) with this reagent. The composition of the chelate is 1:1 and the stability is represented by $\log K = 1.4 \pm 0.2$. We have utilised the formation of the coloured chelates with Chrome Azurol S³ in the colorimetric determination of thorium, uranium³, copper, and aluminium⁴ and this communication describes the determination of beryllium with the same reagent which is highly sensitive for the metal. The reagent has the following structure:

EXPERIMENTAL

Absorbance measurements were carried out with a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer, operated by a Doran's mains unit connected to 220 V/50 cycles a.c. mains; 1 cm thickness of the solutions was employed in all the cases.

1. Proc. Int. Conf. Co-ord. Chem., Sweden, 1962, p. 330.
2. Srivastava and Dey, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, in press
3. Sinha and Dey, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, in press.
4. Srivastava *et al.*, unpublished.

A Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter with a suitable green filter (Klett No. 54) was employed for the colorimetric measurements. The solutions were placed in Klett test tubes of a uniform diameter of 1 cm.

Hydrogen-ion concentration measurements were made with Leeds and Northrup line operated pH indicator, using the glass and calomel electrodes supplied with the instrument. The meter was calibrated from time to time with a standard buffer of pH 6.8. All experiments were carried out in an air-conditioned room maintained at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Solutions of beryllium sulphate ($\text{BeSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, B.D.H. AnalaR) and Chrome Azurol S were prepared in double distilled water. All other reagents used were of analytical grade.

Beer's Law.—To confirm the validity of Beer's law in the system, varying volumes (2, 4, 6, 8, 18 ml) of beryllium sulphate solution were added to a fixed volume of Chrome Azurol S. The pH of the mixtures was adjusted to 6.0 and the total volumes were made to 50 ml by addition of water. The mixtures were allowed to stand for 10 minutes to attain equilibrium. The colour intensity was measured with a photoelectric colorimeter with green filter No. 54 (transmission 520-580 m μ). The system was found to adhere to Beer's law in the range of 0.01 to 0.33 p.p.m. of beryllium (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1. Adherence to Beer's law (total volume 50 ml.)

A. 20 ml 5.0×10^{-4} M Chrome Azurol S:	x ml 1.0×10^{-4} M BeSO_4 .
B. 20 3.33×10^{-4} M	x 6.66×10^{-5} M
C. 20 5.0×10^{-4} M	x 5.0×10^{-5} M
D. 20 2.0×10^{-4} M	x 4.0×10^{-5} M

The rate of colour formation is instantaneous and takes less than 5 minutes to attain full colour intensity.

Influence of Temperature on the Stability of Colour.—A mixture containing $5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ beryllium sulphate and $5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ Chrome Azurol S, when kept for several days at room temperature, retained its absorbance value. On subjecting the same mixture to different temperatures, the chelate was found to remain stable over a wide range of temperature (Table J).

TABLE I

Effect of temperature.

$\text{BeSO}_4 = 5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$. Chrome Azurol S = $5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$. pH of the mixture = 6.0 ± 0.2 .

Temp.	5°	15°	20°	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°	80°	90°	95°
Col. reading	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

Effect of pH.—The effect of pH on the intensity of the colour was studied and it was found that the colour remained stable between pH 4.0 and 6.8 as represented in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2. Variation of colour intensity with pH.
 $\text{BeSO}_4 = 5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$; Chrome Azurol S = $5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$

Sensitivity.—The sensitivity as defined by Sandell⁵ is $0.00045 \gamma/\text{cm}^2$ at $540\text{m}\mu$.

The reagent has been found to be highly sensitive towards beryllium and may be used as a spot reagent for the metal ion.

Influence of Diverse Ions.—The effect of foreign ions in the system may be due to the following causes:

- The foreign ion may react with the reagent.
- The foreign ion may react with the ions to be determined.
- The foreign ion may precipitate because of the pH of the solution.

The influence of various cations and anions was studied with a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter with Klett-filter 54 (Green) and the tolerance limits were calculat-

5. "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 2nd ed., Interscience, New York, 1950.

sd. For tolerance limit has been chosen the concentration of foreign ion which affects the absorbance of the system under investigation by less than $\pm 2\%$. Copper, aluminium, iron, uranium, thorium, zirconium, borate, carbonate, oxalate, and citrate interfered at all concentrations.

TABLE II

Influence of foreign ions.

$\text{BeSO}_4 = 4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$. Chrome Azurol S $= 2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$. pH of the mixture $= 6.0 \pm 0.2$.

Foreign ion.	Added as.	Conc. of ions (p.p.m.).	Obs. change in absorbance (%).	Tolerance limit (p.p.m.).
Li^+	LiCl	140	-4	70
		70	-2	40
Ag^+	AgNO_3	170	-4	81
		81	-2	
Pb^{2+}	$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	120	+6	45
		45	+2	
Hg^{2+}	HgCl_2	64	+4	35
		35	+2	
Bi^{3+}	$\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	32	+6	13
		12	+2	
Cd^{2+}	CdSO_4	50	+4	23
		23	+2	
AsO_3^{3-}	H_3AsO_3	40	+3	25
		25	+2	
Sb^{3+}	SbCl_3	32	-4	15
		16	-2	
Cr^{3+}	CrCl_3	76	+6	20
		20	+2	
Mn^{2+}	MnSO_4	56	+5	24
		24	+2	
Zn^{2+}	ZnCl_2	80	+4	40
		40	+2	
Ni^{2+}	NiSO_4	44	+6	14
		14	+2	
Co^{2+}	$\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	30	+5	13
		12	+2	
Ca^{2+}	CaCl_2	84	+4	45
		45	+2	
Ba^{2+}	BaCl_2	105	+3	75
		75	+2	

TABLE II (contd.)

Foreign ion.	Added as.	Concn. of ions (p.p.m.).	Obs. change in absorbance (%).	Tolerance limit (p.p.m.).
Sr ²⁺	Sr(NO ₃) ₂	90	+6	35
		35	+2	
Mg ²⁺	MgSO ₄	40	+3	30
		30	+2	
Ce ³⁺	Ce ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	30	+5	12
		12	+2	
Ce ⁴⁺	Ce(SO ₄) ₂	35	+3	25
		25	+2	
WO ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ WO ₄	74	+6	28
		28	+2	
MoO ₄ ²⁻	(NH ₄) ₂ MoO ₄	72	+3	45
		45	+2	
VO ₃ ⁻	NH ₄ VO ₃	54	+3	36
		36	+2	
CrO ₄ ²⁻	K ₂ CrO ₄	33	-4	15
		15	-2	
SeO ₃ ²⁻	H ₂ SeO ₃	60	+6	32
		32	+2	
TeO ₃ ²⁻	K ₂ TeO ₃	40	+4	25
		25	+2	
Au ³⁺	AuCl ₃	48	+6	18
		18	+2	
F ⁻	NaF	133	-3	95
		95	-2	
Cl ⁻	KCl	140	-4	80
		80	-3	
Br ⁻	KBr	200	-4	Large excess
		120	-2	
I ⁻	KI	203	-6	75
		75	-2	
ClO ₃ ⁻	KClO ₃	145	-4	83
		83	-2	
NO ₂ ⁻	NaNO ₂	138	-3	93
		93	-2	
NO ₃ ⁻	NaNO ₃	186	-4	Large excess
		120	-2	
CNS ⁻	KCNS	145	-4	87
		87	-2	
S ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	135	-3	90
		90	-2	

TABLE II (contd.)

Foreign ion.	Added as.	Conc. of ions (p.p.m.).	Obs. change in absorbance(%).	Tolerance limit (p.p.m.)
SO ₄ ²⁻	K ₂ SO ₄	192	-4	96
		96	-2	
S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻	K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	385	+5	* Large excess
		140	+2	
Tartrate	K-tart.	150	-5	65
		65	-2	
Acetate	Na-Ac	150	-5	60
		60	-2	
PO ₄ ³⁻	NaH ₂ PO ₄	250	-4	Large excess
		125	-2	

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD,
ALLAHABAD.

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